

3SUM Problem in Linear-logarithmic Time Using Binary Compound Trees

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ABSTRACT

The 3SUM problem was viewed from a singleton point of view for the past time.

SOLUTION

We build the binary tree for each of the elements in binary notation in the given input array, after which we concord the search according to the valid combinations.

REFERENCES

Wikipedia. 3SUM // <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/3SUM>